

README – Raw Data Upload for

Enantiopure Synthesis of Uniform [*n*]Cycloparaphenylene Pillar[5]arene Multi Macrocycles and their Chiroptical Properties

Yannik Sebastian Hansmann, Momoko Sugiura, Marcel Mattes, Sascha Feldmann, Birgit Esser*

The following raw data of various analytical techniques and quantum chemical calculations are compressed into a single .zip file. The files for each compound are sorted into a folder structure, where each method has an own folder. The names (or number) of the molecule folders follow the numbering scheme from the article, but some of the raw data also contain the informal reaction nr. The files and filetypes are as following for each method:

1. Nuclear Magnetic Measurements (NMR)
 - Raw data (Bruker) in the original folder structure, with folder namend according to the respective NMR experiment
2. Mass Spectrometry (MS)
 - Raw data (Bruker – DataAnalysisViewer)
3. UV/Vis absorption spectroscopy
 - .txt files with the wavelength (nm) and extinction coefficient
4. Fluorescence Spectroscopy
 - .txt. files with the wavelength (nm) and fluorecence intensity (excitation wavelength in filename)
5. Quantum Yield
 - .qua raw data from Hamamatsu Quantaurs-QY (C11347). Several compounds in one file, correct measurement number in respective filename
6. Circular Dichroism spectra (CD)
 - .txt files with the wavelength (nm) and molar extinction ($\Delta\epsilon$)
 - .txt files with the wavelength (nm) and g_{abs}
7. Circularly Polarized Luminescence
 - .txt files with the wavelength (nm) and ΔI
 - .txt files with the wavelength (nm) and g_{lum}
8. Quantum chemical calculation
 - (1) Output file and .xyz file of the xtb geometry optimization
 - (2) Results of the sTDDFT calculations based on (1):
 - .out file
 - .uv.xy and .cd.xy files from SpecDis as UV/vis and CD spectra